

**EFFECTS OF RESPONSE TO TEXT INSTRUCTIONAL METHOD ON WRITING
ACHIEVEMENT OF FRESH TERTIARY STUDENTS**

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Abstract

Fresh university students are often at a loss when faced with writing tasks in their new academic environment. This study therefore investigated the effects of the response to text instructional method on the writing achievement of newly admitted university students. Two hundred and forty-eight freshly admitted undergraduates of a university in Owerri, south east Nigeria, participated in the study. The study employed the pre test, post test, control group, quasi-experimental design. One experimental and one control group (consisting of a total of 94 females and 154 males) were used for the study. Students' scores in their pre and post test writing were used as data which were analysed with the use of t-tests, means and standard deviations. The results show that the response to text instructional method had a higher effect on the writing achievement of the students than the conventional method which is the regular mode of instruction. It was recommended that language teachers at the tertiary and other levels of education should adopt the response to text method to enhance the writing proficiency of their students.

Keywords: Text Instructional Method, Writing Achievement. Fresh Tertiary Students, undergraduates, language teachers.
